

Multiplex Network Analysis of Corruption Scandals in Colombian Politics

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Abstract

Natural language processing was used to extract data, which were then employed to generate a corruption network based on some of the most widely known public scandals in Colombia. Different categories were subsequently assigned to the links, turning the network into a multiplex network. After that, several centrality measures were evaluated to characterize the network structure. In order to obtain information about the multiplex characteristics of the network, the existence of an interdependence between a node's degree and its types of relationships was tested. To do so, Monte Carlo methods were used to simulate a joint probability function using the already known frequency properties of the network, in order to evaluate different conditional probabilities and thus conclude that the probabilities are not independent. This has major implications for studying the evolution of the network in relation to its structural properties.

Keywords: Corruption, Networks, Complexity, Multiplex networks, Structural interdependence, Joint probabilities.

1. Introduction

For Vito Tanzi (1998), corruption is the abuse of public power for private benefit. Similarly, for John Kramer (1977), corruption is the behavior of public officials that diverges from the formal duties of a public role in order to serve private ends. Transparency International Internacional (2017) has consistently defined corruption as the abuse of public office for private gain.

These definitions coincide in that corruption is conduct that takes advantage of or abuses a public position in order to obtain a private gain or benefit. This phenomenon has affected many countries in different ways. Colombia is no stranger to corruption, since corruption scandals involving entities, companies, or governmental bodies—public or private—frequently come to light.

According to Newman and Ángel (2017), national and international corruption indicators show a complex panorama for Colombia. In the Corruption Perceptions Index produced in 2016, Colombia obtained a score of 37 points on a scale from 0—higher perceived corruption—to 100—lower perceived corruption. Between 2009 and 2016, 3966 cases were registered in the accusatory oral criminal justice system, related to different forms of corruption, i.e., about 500 per year.

There are different national and international organizations that play a crucial role in the fight against this social problem. Internationally, the UN promotes the fight against corruption through the United Nations Convention against Corruption (UNCAC), which is the first legally binding global instrument to prevent and combat corruption. The World Bank, through programs and financing, promotes transparent governance and integrity in recipient countries, and supports institutional strengthening initiatives to prevent and combat corruption. World Bank (2021). Transparency International is also an organization dedicated to combating corruption glob-

ally. It conducts research, promotes transparency and ethical standards, and advocates for accountability across all sectors of society. Transparency International also produces the Corruption Perceptions Index, which evaluates perceived corruption in different countries.

In Colombia, the Office of the Inspector General (Procuraduría General de la Nación) is an entity responsible for safeguarding administrative morality and transparency in the public sector. Procuraduría de la Nación (2023). The Office of the Comptroller General (Contraloría General de la República) is responsible for fiscal oversight. Its goal is to prevent and detect irregularities in public management, including corruption cases, through auditing and oversight of State resources. Also, the Administrative Department of the Public Service, whose mission is to promote efficiency, transparency, and ethics in the Colombian public service. This agency formulates and supervises human talent management policies in the public sector, in order to prevent corruption and improve service quality. Función Pública (2023).

These and other national institutions are key in the fight against corruption in Colombia. However, corruption is complex and affects multiple areas of society. Therefore, addressing this challenge comprehensively requires a multidisciplinary perspective.

Various areas of knowledge such as political science, sociology, anthropology, psychology, law, and economics have produced contributions on this phenomenon and have pointed out the economic, political, and social impacts it generates.

Nowadays, the complexity approach and network science are added, allowing corruption to be analyzed from a systemic perspective. These disciplines provide tools to visualize and understand the interconnections and underlying dynamics in corruption networks, revealing the complexity of this phenomenon and opening new opportunities for its study and combat.

In this project, recent advances in natural language process-

ing and machine learning were leveraged to analyze efficiently and at scale the large amount of textual information related to scandals. Language models, such as GPT-3.5, provided a sophisticated way to interpret and analyze text Wadhwa et al. (2023), allowing entities and relationships to be extracted and categorized from the abundant data in news and articles related to these scandals. Through this approach, it became possible to build a network that includes, as nodes, the actors mentioned in news about corruption scandals, and as relationships, the links found in the form of verbal phrases.

1.1. State of the Art

1.1.1. Corruption and Complexity

For several decades, different indices and measures have been implemented in the study of corruption, enabling quantitative analyses of this social problem. Rose-Ackerman (1999).

Subsequently, authors such as D’Orsogna and Perc (2015) began to implement tools from statistical mechanics to the study of corruption. However, according to Gómez-Gardeñes et al. (2020), the authors argue that traditional approaches lack analytical tools to handle the structural and dynamic aspects that characterize modern social, political, and technological systems where corruption takes place. They point out that corruption is a systemic and adaptive phenomenon that requires comprehensive and multidisciplinary approaches for its prevention and effective combat. In response, they suggest that complex systems have emerged as an integrative framework to study highly adaptive phenomena in natural environments.

1.1.2. Corruption Networks

When network science begins to be applied to the study of corruption, social network analysis techniques are used to investigate connections and interactions between corrupt actors in various contexts, such as governments and companies. This can be seen in Wang (2020), where they study the social network of corruption in China to find behavioral patterns.

Then, researchers begin to use simulation models to study how corruption spreads in networks. These models help to understand factors that contribute to the persistence of corruption and to identify prevention and detection strategies. Mahler-Hutter (2009). In parallel, these models have helped to build and study the dynamics and propagation of these networks. Ribeiro et al. (2018)

Gradually, there is an increase in multidisciplinary collaboration to address the problem of corruption, and network analysis methods are applied to investigate political networks and power structures in relation to corruption. Gonzalez et al. (2018).

The study of corruption through network science continues to evolve and expand. Increasingly sophisticated approaches are used, such as multilayer analysis and the analysis of money and resource flows, to understand the dynamics and effects of corruption in different systems. Diviák et al. (2019).

1.1.3. Corruption Networks in Colombia

In Colombia, a pioneering study has addressed the phenomenon of political corruption from an economic perspective,

starting from Public Choice analysis and incorporating network analysis to characterize the structural complexity that defines processes of political corruption, clientelism, and judicial favoritism in Colombia, in the case of the Cartel de la Toga. Gonzalez et al. (2018).

2. Methodology and Data

Due to the possibility of representing systems composed of agents and their relationships through network theory, it has been possible to study different kinds of social systems, such as corruption networks. In this research project, the scandal network of corruption in Colombian politics was analyzed.

Here we present a brief description of each corruption case:

- **AgroIngreso Seguro:** A corruption scandal that emerged in Colombia in 2009, where it was revealed that government subsidies intended to support small farmers were being irregularly diverted to large landowners and political figures.
- **Cartel de la toga:** A corruption case involving magistrates in the Colombian judicial system, in which the sale of judicial rulings and influence peddling in exchange for bribes were reported.
- **Centros Poblados Case:** This corruption case emerged in 2021 in Colombia. It involves irregularities in a contract of 1.07 trillion pesos for the installation of free internet in rural areas, and resulted in the arrest of several public officials and contractors.
- **Reficar Scandal:** One of the largest corruption scandals in Colombia’s history. Reficar, a subsidiary of the Colombian state oil company, embezzled billions of dollars in the remodeling of an oil refinery.
- **Odebrecht Case:** Odebrecht, a Brazilian construction company, paid millions of dollars in bribes to Colombian politicians and officials to obtain infrastructure contracts. The scandal broke in 2016 and led to the conviction of numerous high-level politicians and officials in Colombia.
- **Contracting Carousel:** This scandal emerged in Bogotá in 2010, when it was discovered that politicians and contractors were illicitly inflating the price of public works contracts for personal enrichment. Losses for the city were estimated at hundreds of millions of dollars.

Once the scandals were selected, a careful search for news related to each one was conducted. This search was not limited to finding mere mentions of the events; instead, it sought complete and detailed coverage of each scandal. Among the many news pieces that can arise from this search, the 15 most relevant were selected, with preference given to those published by recognized media outlets.

With the news articles in hand, the textual content was downloaded using the Python library BeautifulSoup. This text, in its rawest form and without additional modifications or formatting,

was the material submitted to processing by a language model called GPT-3.5.

This language model processes the news texts and performs two crucial tasks. First, it identifies and classifies the entities present in the text, whether organizations or individuals. Second, the model searches for relationships among these entities. Thus, at the end of this process, one obtains a list of entities and a set of relationships among them, all extracted directly from the selected news articles.

However, before proceeding with data analysis, it is necessary to carry out a cleaning and curation phase. In this stage, the Python library spaCy was used to remove all entities that do not correspond to individuals. spaCy employs a named entity recognition component based on transitions that identifies token spans without overlaps. Although this algorithm may not be ideal for all tasks—because it assumes that the most crucial information about entities will be near the first tokens and optimizes overall entity accuracy, which can be inefficient if entities are long or if there is disagreement about their boundaries—it was used here as part of the cleaning process. Subsequently, duplicate relationships were removed. This step ensures that the data used for analysis are unique and relevant.

The selected relationships were classified into five distinct categories: influenceRelations, corruptionRelations, investigationRelations, familyRelations, and professionalRelations. Each category represents a specific type of connection among individuals or entities within the dataset.

1. Influence Relations: These correspond to resource transfers and collaboration. This is supported by the idea that “The transfer or exchange of resources (if reciprocal) is the principal component of numerous forms of organized criminal activity” Bright et al. (2015) and that “Links in this dimension can be broadly defined as intentional interactions, involving communication that may be both direct (face-to-face) and indirect (e.g., phone calls, emails)” Krebs (2002).

2. Corruption Relations: These are associated with resource transfers, based on the claim that “In our case, the main resources transferred are money in the form of bribes or kickbacks for politicians and manipulated contracts for business-people” Bright et al. (2015).

3. Investigation Relations: Although not explicitly mentioned in the cited literature, these could be considered part of collaboration, since this type of relation requires information exchange and cooperation to carry out an investigation. This is based on the description that “Links in this dimension can be broadly defined as intentional interactions, involving communication that may be both direct (face-to-face) and indirect (e.g., phone calls, emails)” Krebs (2002).

4. Family Relations: These fall within the category of pre-existing ties, as evidenced by the statement that “Pre-existing ties, i.e., ties established prior to the criminal act itself, can be crucial sources of trust... pre-existing ties can take the form of kinship relationships” Morselli and Roy (2008).

5. Professional Relations: These are also categorized as pre-existing ties, according to the assertion that “Pre-existing ties include mutual membership on a corporate board of directors” Morselli and Roy (2008).

Each of these steps was repeated for each of the selected corruption scandals. Thus, at the end of this methodology, one obtains a view of the network of corruption scandals in Colombia, ready to be analyzed and studied.

2.1. Tools Used

2.1.1. Network Measures

To analyze the structures and patterns of the corruption networks emerging from the data, various network metrics were used. These metrics facilitate understanding of structure, cohesion, and network distribution, and help identify the most influential nodes.

1. Degree: This centrality metric counts the number of links a node has with other nodes in the network. It can be expressed as:

$$k_i = \sum_j A_{ij}$$

where A_{ij} is the entry of the adjacency matrix that connects nodes i and j . Newman (2010).

2. Betweenness: This quantifies how many times a node acts as a “bridge” along the shortest path between two other nodes. It is calculated as:

$$C_B(v) = \sum_{s,t \in V} \frac{\sigma(s,t|v)}{\sigma(s,t)}$$

where $\sigma(s,t)$ is the total number of shortest paths from s to t and $\sigma(s,t|v)$ is the number of those paths that pass through v . Brandes (2001).

3. Clustering: This indicates the tendency of nodes to cluster. A high clustering coefficient can indicate densely connected subnetworks.

$$C_i = \frac{2E_i}{k_i(k_i - 1)}$$

where E_i is the number of links among the neighbors of node i . Watts and Strogatz (1998).

4. Closeness: This refers to the average proximity of a node to all other nodes.

$$C(x) = \frac{1}{\sum_y d(y,x)}$$

where $d(y,x)$ is the shortest distance from y to x . Bavelas (1950)

5. Average Geodesic Distance: This is the average length of the shortest path between each pair of nodes.

$$L = \frac{1}{n(n-1)} \sum_{i \neq j} d_{ij}$$

where d_{ij} is the shortest distance between nodes i and j . Newman (2003).

6. Modularity: This evaluates the network structure by dividing it into modules or communities.

$$Q = \frac{1}{2m} \sum_{vw} [A_{vw} - \frac{k_v k_w}{2m}] \delta(c_v, c_w)$$

where A_{vw} are the adjacency matrix elements, k_v and k_w are the degrees of nodes v and w , m is the total number of links, c_v and c_w are the communities of the nodes, and $\delta(c_v, c_w)$ is 1 if v and w are in the same community and 0 otherwise. Newman (2006).

2.1.2. Frequency Counting

Frequencies and probabilities are directly related. Probability can be computed from event frequencies. If one has a set of events, each with its own frequency, it is possible to convert those frequencies into probabilities. The probability of a specific event is simply the frequency of that event divided by the sum of the frequencies of all events.

Mathematically, if an event E has frequency $f(E)$ in N total experiments, then the probability $P(E)$ is computed as:

$$P(E) = \frac{f(E)}{N}$$

2.1.3. Information Theory and Surprise Factor

Shannon entropy is a quantitative measure of uncertainty in a probability distribution; it is used to quantify the uncertainty associated with a random variable:

$$H(x) = - \sum P(x) \log P(x)$$

The surprise factor is a related concept that quantifies how surprising or unexpected a particular event is, given what is known Varley (2023). An event that is very probable according to the model or prior knowledge has a low surprise factor, while an event that is very unlikely has a high surprise factor. This surprise factor is defined as:

$$h(x) = \log \left(\frac{1}{P(x)} \right) \quad (1)$$

2.1.4. Assigning Probabilities to the Degree Distribution and the Betweenness Distribution

Once a degree distribution is obtained—where, according to node degrees, one counts how many nodes with that degree value are present in the network—it is possible to transform this distribution into a probability function; this probability function states the probability that a node exhibits a given degree. ??

$$P(k) = \frac{\alpha}{f_{\max} k^\beta} \quad (2)$$

2.1.5. Joint and Conditional Probabilities and Bayes' Theorem

Joint probabilities refer to the probability that two or more events occur simultaneously. If there are two independent events A and B , the joint probability that both occur is denoted as $P(A \cap B)$, and is computed by multiplying their individual probabilities:

$$P(A \cap B) = P(A)P(B)$$

If the events are dependent, conditional probability must be defined to compute the joint probability.

Conditional probabilities are used to compute the probability that an event occurs given that another event has already occurred. They are denoted as $P(A|B)$, which is the probability that A occurs given that B has occurred. The expression to compute conditional probability is:

$$P(A|B) = \frac{P(A \cap B)}{P(B)}$$

This equation indicates that the conditional probability of A given B is equal to the joint probability of A and B divided by the probability of B . Canavos (1994).

Bayes' theorem is a tool that allows updating prior knowledge about an event when new relevant information is obtained. It is used to compute conditional probabilities in the reverse direction. The equation for Bayes' theorem is:

$$P(A|B) = \frac{P(B|A)P(A)}{P(B)} \quad (3)$$

2.1.6. Multiplex Networks

Multiplex networks are those in which nodes interact through multiple layers of relationships. There are many systems that can be modeled as multiplex networks; for example, neurons are connected via chemical synapses and electrical synapses CITA. To model this type of network there are several approaches; in this work, the multilinear approach is used.

Multiplex networks with multiple layers are considered as many simple networks, denoted as the network of layer α and represented by G_α . Each of these networks is composed of N nodes and M_α links. Described in this way, it is possible to define a multilinear generalization of the adjacency matrix Cozzo et al. (2018), whose components are denoted a_{ij}^α , and for unweighted multiplex networks takes value 1 if there is a link between nodes i, j in layer α . The multiplex network model used in this work is illustrated in the following image:

Figure 1: Example of a multiplex network

Multiplex networks are useful in the analysis of corruption networks because they provide a more realistic and detailed view of social reality. They allow differentiation between different types of relationships and exchanges among actors, which is essential for understanding criminal activities and how networks play a role in their organization. The multiplicity of relationships can be an important factor in illegal environments,

where it compensates for the lack of formal institutions. A simplex analysis of aggregated networks can lead to an over- or underestimation of the prominence of individual actors. An actor can be central in one dimension but peripheral in others, which would incorrectly make it appear unimportant in the aggregated simplex network. Diviák et al. (2019).

3. Results and Discussion

Once the network was completed by filtering the provided articles and cleaning some repeated data 2, it was observed that in the graph generated in networkx, links were differentiated by the name assigned to them. However, these names did not represent categories with practical implications; rather, they were only qualitative differentiations of connections. Therefore, using these names, different categories were created in order to make the graph multiplex.

Figure 2: Graph of the network of the six corruption scandals studied

This multiplex graph is composed of 191 nodes and 312 links, which corresponds to a very low density ($\rho = 0.0085$). Also, at first glance, its shape appears to have characteristics typical of corruption networks reported for other countries in Martins et al. (2022). In addition, the average agent in the network has between 3 and 4 connections ($K_{average} = 3.26$). On the other hand, the multiplex graph has 6 types of links, which are: **Influence Relationship, Corruption Relationship, Family Relationship, Investigation Relationship, Family relationship** and **Unknown Relationship**.

Partially assuming that relationship types do not influence classical centrality measures, it is possible, for a moment, to treat the network as if all its connections belonged to a single category. In this way, several centrality measures were obtained, shedding light on the network structure and actor importance, such as degree 6, betweenness 3, closeness 4, among others:

In order to extract information from multiplex networks, the number of links between nodes was counted according to relationship type. This was then used to discuss which relationships are more frequent than others and also to assign probabilities in

Figure 3: Betweenness levels for different agents in the network

Figure 4: Closeness levels for different agents in the network

case one wants to construct a network with the same frequency of appearance of multiplex links. That is, a distribution was built showing the probability of encountering a given relationship type if one picks a random link in the network.

From these probabilities it was possible to compute the entropy for each relationship type and the overall entropy for the probability distribution (2.109 bits). Then, based on this probability distribution, it was also possible to compute the surprise factor, 1; which can be seen in the plot 5. As shown, the relationship that tends to repeat most in the network is the family relationship, followed by the corruption and professional relationships. Observing this plot makes it possible to identify which type of relationship is most expected; it also suggests which types of political relationships should receive much more attention to prevent the creation of a robust network that makes dismantling illicit actors more difficult.

To obtain the degree distribution, the number of neighbors of each node in the network was counted and then a histogram was created that provides information about how often the scenario occurs in which a node has a certain degree. As expected, this behavior appeared to be governed by a power law, where many nodes have few neighbors and very few nodes have many neighbors. 6

Approximately, from the frequency values associated with degrees, it is possible to use these points to fit a power law and find a function defined on $[1, \infty)$ (1 being the minimum degree a node can exhibit) that describes the probability of finding a node with a given degree in the network $P(K)$. 7 Clearly, if one wants an exact probability function, the first step is to

Figure 5: Surprise factor for the probability distribution of relationship types in the network

Figure 6: Histogram of the number of nodes with a given degree

obtain a probability density function, not by normalizing a fit obtained from frequency data, but by dividing each frequency by the total number of times a node with that degree appears in the network (sum of all frequencies). In this way, one obtains a discrete probability density function that integrates to 1, and which—under certain considerations and a fit—could be made continuous and then integrated over an interval to obtain an exact probability. However, for simplicity and lack of time, an approximate form was used, which does not differ much in the results and preserves the core idea of extracting information from multiplex networks.

Since there is a probability function and a probability distribution, it is pertinent to ask what the probability is that a random node has a certain degree or that its degree lies in a region, given that it is connected to some node through a specific relationship type ($P(K = 5|r = \textit{Familiar'})$); or even to continue asking questions based on conditional factors, in order to understand how part of the degree or betweenness structure relates to the structure of multiplex relationship types.

Figure 7: Approximate probability function $P(k)$

Thus, the question arises: is a node's degree in any way related to the types of connections it may have? To answer this question, Bayes' theorem 3 can be used. In the present case, if both probabilities are independent, the conditional probability result would not be influenced by the relationship and would be equal to the probability of only one part:

$$\begin{aligned}
 P(K = 5|r = \textit{Familiar'}) &= \frac{P(K = 5, r = \textit{Familiar'})}{P(r = \textit{Familiar'})} \quad (4) \\
 &= \frac{P(K = 5)P(r = \textit{Familiar'})}{P(r = \textit{Familiar'})} \\
 &= P(K = 5)
 \end{aligned}$$

To verify whether this is the case and conclude whether there is interdependence between centrality values and relationship types in this network, a joint probability distribution was created via a Monte Carlo method. In this way, following the probability distribution of multiplex relationship types and the frequencies with which nodes appear according to their degree, it was possible to construct a generator of random values and thus build a joint space with points generated according to the respective distributions, and then assign probabilities. 8

Figure 8: Joint space of random variables to generate joint probabilities

Once the joint space was obtained, it was possible to compute joint probabilities by counting points relative to the total number of points generated in the space. In this way, to test that

there is a relationship between degree and link types, it was decided to compute $P(K = 2|r = 'Influencia')$, which resulted in 60.29%, a value very different from what would be obtained if independence were assumed, namely 39.63%. This finding is very important, as it allows a deeper understanding of the structure of this network.

This has major implications in the case of having a much larger corruption network spanning political scandals beyond those selected for this work. If one considers that, in some way, one could predict network evolution based on the types of connections that could arise from known structural frequencies, then it would also be possible to derive information about how alternatives for combating and preventing corruption could be generated. For instance, one could study ahead of time relationship structures that might maximize the types of links that generate scenarios where corruption is taking place. However, more studies are needed regarding the structural characteristics of political scenarios, especially corruption, and what other ways more precise and clearer conclusions can be extracted to shed light on this aspect.

4. Conclusions

In this study, the structure of a political corruption network was explored using network analysis techniques and statistics to extract meaningful information about relationships between actors and the nature of their interactions. Through this research, it was found that the network is highly complex and multiplex, with different relationship types that intertwine and overlap in ways that are not immediately evident at first glance.

It was found that family and corruption relationships are the most prevalent in the network, suggesting that family ties and corrupt activities are deeply embedded in the network structure. However, it was also observed that the network has a very low density, indicating that most actors in the network have only a few connections. This suggests that, although corruption may be widespread, it is concentrated in a small number of key actors.

By analyzing the network centrality measures, it was discovered that there are a small number of nodes with high betweenness and closeness, indicating that these actors may play an important role in facilitating corruption in the network. These actors may be key targets for interventions aimed at dismantling the corruption network.

In addition, Monte Carlo simulation techniques were used to explore the relationship between a node's degree and the types of relationships it has. The results suggest that there is interdependence between these two characteristics, indicating that the network structure and the nature of relationships among actors are not independent. This finding has important implications for understanding how the corruption network forms and evolves.

The corruption network analysis revealed a set of key characteristics that could be useful for informing corruption prevention and combat strategies. However, several areas requiring further research were also identified, including the need for

more detailed studies on the structural characteristics of corruption networks and the search for more precise methods to extract information from these networks. Despite these challenges, this work is believed to provide a valuable starting point for future research in this field.

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